

PCIe Monitoring for Secure Code Execution in Heterogeneous System Architectures

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Abstract—Heterogeneous architectures, such as GPUs, and FPGAs, are now widely used in data centers to handle demanding computational tasks. However, their growing adoption introduces new attack surfaces. For example, a malicious user could exploit a GPU by running unauthorized workloads—such as a crypto miner—causing performance degradation or making the resource unavailable. This work introduces a novel approach for detecting attacks in heterogeneous systems by monitoring PCIe traffic at the hardware level, from the host to the GPU accelerator. By inspecting runtime data and code transfers, the system can identify potentially malicious behavior using rule-based detection. A custom monitoring tool is implemented on an MPSoC-based emulation platform, leveraging predefined GPU instruction patterns to detect crypto miners. Fully hardware-based, the tool is scalable and adds no runtime overhead. The PCIe monitor achieves better performance than the corresponding state-of-the-art, CPU-based implementation by an overall speedup of $x1.55$, and it is more energy efficient by 543 times while occupying limited hardware resources.

Index Terms—Security, Hardware security, FPGA, GPU, PCIe, mining

I. INTRODUCTION

Heterogeneous system architectures are gaining popularity for handling complex, high-load computational tasks. Many companies operate large data centers with thousands of heterogeneous systems, enabling developers to run applications on GPUs, FPGAs, or TPUs. However, the growing adoption of these systems has introduced a significant attack surface with various potential threats. GPU vulnerabilities and their exploitation are practical risks, with malicious actors potentially using miners to overload GPUs, making them unavailable for critical operations.

Companies, such as Microsoft and CISCO, report incidents [1] [2] concerning the use of their GPUs to execute crypto miners without the companies' knowledge and permission. The mitigation used is mainly focused on using software tools that can always be bypassed or disabled by a malicious user, letting their GPUs be exposed to such attacks.

This work introduces a novel method for detecting attacks in heterogeneous systems by monitoring PCIe traffic at a lower-level, i.e. hardware-level, from the host to the corresponding

PCIe endpoint, using a custom hardware module. The PCIe monitoring tool provides the runtime monitoring of instruction code in the PCIe endpoint using a pattern-matching algorithm for optimal performance. It alerts the system when a malicious pattern is found in the data transferred to the PCIe endpoint in a similar way to that of an intrusion detection system (IDS) based on a set of rules. This work introduces a technology for PCIe traffic monitoring. It emulates a heterogeneous CPU-GPU system that hosts GPU miners operating on the GPU side and uses a set of rules composed of patterns present in GPU instructions for detection purposes. The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

- We propose a runtime monitoring mechanism for the PCIe protocol.
- We develop a custom set of rules composed of patterns of GPU instructions to detect GPU miners.
- We show that the monitoring system does not add any extra processing overhead in the execution of GPU applications since it is implemented entirely on hardware.
- We achieve better detection latency performance, by a factor of $1.55x$, compared to state-of-the-art software tools (such as the YARA tool).
- Our implementation requires limited hardware resources.

II. RELATED WORK

Recently, the increasing utilization of GPUs has emerged as a significant threat to their security as they have evolved from being used for simple graphics tasks, such as video and gaming, to powerful computational units for heavy load tasks, for example, training CNN, DNN, and machine learning tasks. Consequently, many researchers have begun to explore the capabilities of such attack vectors, focusing on GPU vulnerabilities, GPU attacks, and GPU defense mechanisms.

Miele et al. [5] presents a preliminary analysis of buffer overflow vulnerabilities in the CUDA API running on GPUs. Its work demonstrates how an attacker can overrun a buffer to corrupt sensitive data or steer the execution flow by overwriting function pointers, e.g., manipulating the virtual table of a C++ object. Di et al. [6] explore security vulnerabilities

of CUDA from multiple dimensions. Their work shows a study on GPU stack revealing stack, heap integer, and function pointer overflow can be exploited by manipulating different memory spaces so different threads, blocks, and kernels can be overwritten with other content. Park et al. [15] present a novel attack method that makes deep learning predictions no longer different from random guessing by degrading the accuracy of the predictions. Their work demonstrates the first practical attack that directly exploits deep learning frameworks through memory manipulation of GPU devices. Their attack works on three popular deep learning frameworks, TensorFlow, CNTK, and Caffe, running on CUDA. Mingtian Tan et al. [10] presents a timing attack that measures PCIe congestion and infers the keystroke timings of the victim, identifying the webpage that is rendered on the GPU, and the ML model that runs on the GPU.

Erb et al. [13] describe a tool to detect buffer overflows caused by GPU kernels performing canary checks similar to the CPU. Their work is focused on GPU memory buffer overflows in AMD GPUs, and for this reason, their tool wraps OpenCL API calls and alerts users to any kernel that writes outside of the memory buffer. Di et al. [14] propose an efficient buffer overflow detector named GMODx, a runtime software system that can detect GPU buffer overflow. This tool monitors allocated memory based on a canary-based design, using several techniques such as delayed memory-free, efficient memory reallocation, garbage collections, and others, improving performance and decreasing overhead compared to other detectors.

In the last couple of years, Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) have gained tremendous ground in GPUs as a security defense mechanism, and many researchers have developed and implemented proof-of-concept tools to explore the concept of GPU TEEs. Volos et al. [4] propose a GPU TEE to isolate the execution of the kernels from other code running on the GPU and all software on the host. It proposes modifications in the peripheral components, such as the GPU’s command processor, with no changes to existing CPUs, GPU cores, or the GPU’s MMU and memory controller. It also proposes extensions to the CUDA runtime for securely copying data and executing kernels on the GPU. Their work is implemented by emulating the new hardware features of the GPU and shows an overhead of around 17%-33%. Jang et al. [3] propose a novel hardware and software architecture as a trusted execution environment. It does not require modifications to the GPU architecture to offer protection. Instead, it provides security by modifying the I/O interconnect between the CPU and GPU and refactoring the GPU device driver to work within the CPU-trusted environment. Their work implements the proposed architecture on an emulated machine with KVM and QEMU, showing that the performance overhead for security is curtailed to 26% on average.

A. Our Approach

Building upon the rise of GPU vulnerabilities and the need for an effective way to detect malicious applications targeting

Fig. 1. MPSoC-FPGA Heterogeneous Setup

GPUs, a novel notion of defense mechanism can emerge as a solution to ensure secure code execution in heterogeneous system architectures, such as CPU-FPGA-GPU, FPGA-GPU and many more. Monitoring the PCIe traffic of instructions being transferred from a host, e.g. a CPU, to a GPU, can become an effective defense against various attacks.

The state-of-the-art defense approach, both in industry and academia, to ensure secure code execution in heterogeneous systems architectures is either through the use of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs), which add extra overhead for the system, or static analysis of the binary executable code using product tools such as YARA and SNORT. Moreover, a PCIe analyzer can be used to analyze the PCIe traffic of TLP packets using a distinct tool which, nevertheless, is expensive [17]. Our proposed approach focuses on PCIe monitoring for secure code execution in heterogeneous system architectures. It uses an FPGA-based prototype for demonstration purposes to emulate a heterogeneous system architecture consisting of CPU-GPU pair. The aim is to develop a monitoring system that ensures secure and efficient code execution by monitoring the PCIe data traffic between the CPU and GPU and detecting any security issues during runtime. The system will leverage specific GPU instruction patterns of malicious programs at the machine level to detect any attempt to attack the GPU. The proposed approach is expected to enhance the security of heterogeneous system architectures, which are becoming increasingly popular in various fields, including machine learning, data analytics, and high-performance computing.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system emulates a heterogeneous system architecture composed of one CPU and one GPU, by utilizing two different FPGA-based development boards to represent them. The CPU side is emulated using an AMD/Xilinx ZCU102 MPSoC board that features 4 ARM A35 processor cores while the GPU-endpoint side is emulated using an AMD/Xilinx KC705 FPGA board that hosts both the endpoint

Fig. 2. Block Diagram of system's emulation with the monitoring tool

Fig. 3. Hardware Architecture of the PCIe endpoint

functionality as well as the PCIe monitoring module (Fig. 1). The module aims to monitor the GPU code that is sent for execution by the CPU at runtime and detect any malicious patterns of instructions on the machine level. In addition, Figure 2 illustrates the system's block diagram representation.

A. Host

The host is implemented on a ZCU102 development board, mainly using its processor and PCIe interconnect. It supports the functionalities required for data (instruction) transfers from the CPU to the emulated GPU endpoint through the PCIe port interface. The Operating System (OS) running on the host has been developed using an embedded OS development tool, i.e. Petalinux, which supports the CPU architecture of ZCU102 and its configurations on the Linux kernel to enable the PCIe libraries and packages on the system. In addition, a PCIe driver, needed for interfacing with the implementation of the PCIe endpoint, i.e. emulated GPU, was obtained and used from the official GitHub repository of Xilinx.

B. PCIe Endpoint

The PCIe endpoint emulates the functionality of the GPU and the custom monitoring tool using an FPGA hosted on the KC705 development board. It comprises several Intellectual Property (IP) cores, the most important of which being *i*) the PCIe IP core, *ii*) the custom monitoring IP core, and *iii*) the core for GPU emulation.

Figure 3 illustrates the hardware design of the PCIe endpoint. There are three main components: the PCIe interface, the PCIe monitor, and the GPU emulation. It can be observed that the flow of PCIe traffic is from the PCIe Interface to the PCIe monitor and then to GPU Emulation.

Fig. 4. Hardware Architecture of the Monitoring Tool

The monitoring tool has been implemented and developed using the Aho-Corasick (AC) algorithm, with some modifications to adapt it for GPU instructions instead of characters as input. The monitoring tool comprises several Aho-Corasick IP cores according to the PCIe stream channels of the PCIe interface that are being used. Figure 4 illustrates the hardware architecture of the monitoring tool at an abstract level.

The architecture of the Aho-Corasick algorithm consists of a pipeline architecture as presented in Figure 5. The GPU instructions are streamed as input by the host CPU through the PCIe channels to the Aho-Corasick IP cores. In addition, malicious patterns of GPU instructions are being loaded to the Aho-Corasick module in local memory as the rules in which the Aho-Corasick algorithm operates. The implemented architecture of each of the Aho-Corasick IP cores consists of two high-level pipeline stages, which are internally split into two lower-level pipeline stages. The processing results from the second pipeline stage are streamed back to the host CPU through the PCIe channels. The pipeline stages implement a low-level Finite State Machine (FSM), responsible for moving into the stored tree structure according to the streaming input data. Traversing the stored tree structure produces a final score, which indicates the number of successful matches between runtime and stored/reference data and, therefore, the number of malicious patterns of instructions. The overall design of the PCIe endpoint consists of an XDMA IP core, an Aho-Corasick (AC) core, an AXI Interconnect, an AXI BRAM controller, a Block Memory Generator, and an AXI DMA Stream. The PCIe interface contains the XDMA IP core responsible for communication through PCIe, the AXI stream FIFO IP cores, and the utility buffer used for the PCIe reference clock. The PCIe monitor block comprises two Aho-Corasick IP cores to monitor the PCIe traffic and two AXI stream Broadcaster IP cores to broadcast the PCIe traffic to the GPU emulation concurrently with the monitoring. Last but not least, the GPU emulation contains one BRAM to store the GPU executable code as it would happen to an actual GPU, two AXI stream DMA engines to convert the AXI stream into an AXI memory mapped interface, two AXI BRAM Controllers to send the GPU executable code from the DMA to the BRAM and, finally, an AXI interconnect for the interconnection of the two AXI DMA with the PCIe interface to set up some configurations of the DMA.

Fig. 5. Hardware Architecture of Aho-Corasick IP core

Fig. 6. Instructions of Miners (%)

C. Malicious GPU patterns

The discovery of the GPU instructions, which may be a threat due to their malicious intentions, is being made to protect GPUs from potential DoS (Denial of Service) attacks originating from the execution of GPU Miners. It is widespread to deploy a GPU miner into a system to overload GPU usage and, as a result, render the heterogeneous system out-of-service.

The examined miners are the xmrMiner¹, yadaGPUminer², a simple GPU miner³, and the Blake’s2 miner⁴. Due to space constraints, we present our findings for two miners, i.e., xmrMiner and yadaGPUminer. They were compared with a variety of regular programs, from sorting algorithms to AI and genetic algorithms, to ensure that there is diversity in the samples and that the patterns discovered in the miners are not random. The GPU programs have been compiled using NVIDIA’s compiler nvcc version 10.4 for GPUs supporting the architecture SM30 (Kepler Architecture) because it is a widespread architecture in NVIDIA’s GPUs.

Initially, both regular programs and miners are analyzed at the instruction level to observe if any group of instructions is more commonly used in miners and extract any valuable statistical pieces of information. Developing a simple Python and bash script and using NVIDIA’s cuobjdump tool to extract the GPU assembly commands of each GPU program revealed some interesting statistics. Hence, Figure 6 shows that instructions SHF and LOP appear at a 20% of the total instructions of a normal program while at a rate of 40% in the case of miners.

¹<https://github.com/xmrMiner/xmrMiner>

²<https://github.com/pdxwebdev/yadagpuminer>

³https://github.com/geedo0/cuda_bitcoin_miner

⁴<https://github.com/oxencoin/ccminer-blake2s>

Fig. 7. Instructions of programs (%)

Furthermore, the same analysis of GPU instructions is performed on simple GPU programs. Figure 7 shows the percentage of the exact GPU instructions SHF and LOP, which were found to appear at a higher rate in the GPU miners. It can be observed that the percentage of the LOP instruction occurs in a percentage less than 10% and the SHF instruction less than 5%. As a result, it can be considered that the possibility of the appearance of the SHF and LOP instructions in a GPU miner is higher than that of a simple GPU program and approximately around $x4$ times more possible. This led to examining the GPU miner code of instructions for patterns of instructions containing the LOP and SHF.

Examining and extracting malicious patterns of GPU instructions that declare the use of GPU miners was achieved using the well-known framework SPMF with some modifications [18]. It mined frequent closed sequential patterns using the BIDE+ algorithm. Due to the nature of mining algorithms examining for patterns, all the GPU instructions of a GPU miner executable program would require a tremendous amount of time, so a slightly different methodology was followed. In addition, it is observed in GPU code that every several instructions, a control code is sent after the instructions, which depends on GPU architecture. For instance, in the Kepler architecture of a GPU, the CPU sends a control code for every 7 GPU instructions. As a result, the patterns of GPU instructions mined within the framework were between every 7 GPU instructions.

Table I denotes as *True* or *False* whether the GPU miner has the corresponding pattern of instructions in its code. The table also illustrates which pattern may be in simple GPU programs and is considered as a false positive.

IV. EVALUATION

The evaluation of the PCIe monitoring system involves verifying the system’s functional demands and calculating the performance metrics. The functional verification process cross-validates the simulation results with the FPGA board results. In contrast, the performance evaluation of the FPGA board consist of calculating (i) the overall design’s power and energy consumption, and (ii) the computational throughput and latency of the IP cores of the Aho-Corasick algorithm. The process of verifying the functional demands of the PCIe

TABLE I
THE MALICIOUS GPU PATTERNS OF INSTRUCTIONS IN MINERS (SELECTED) AND GPU PROGRAMS.

Malicious GPU Patterns	xmrMiner	yadaGPUMiner	Astar	Compression	MergeSort	Sieve	cumf als	genetic	hash table	Radix sort
SHF SHF LOP	True	True	False	False	False	False	False	False	False	False
SHF LOP SHF	True	True	False	False	False	True	False	False	False	False
SHF LOP LOP	True	True	False	False	False	True	False	False	False	False
LOP SHF SHF	True	True	False	False	False	False	False	False	False	False
LOP SHF LOP	True	True	False	False	False	True	False	False	False	False
LOP LOP SHF	True	True	False	False	False	True	False	False	False	False
LOP LOP LOP	True	True	False	False	True	True	True	True	False	False
LOP LOP LOP LOP	True	True	False	False	False	False	False	True	False	False

monitoring system involves cross-validating many samples of inputs containing typical cases and edge cases with the results taken from the FPGA board using a system Integrated Logic Analyzer (System ILA) to check the most important signals of the IP core of Aho-Corasick. The input samples include both benign cases, where no malicious GPU code patterns are present, and cases containing between 1-8 distinct malicious patterns. Those malicious patterns have been extracted from real GPU code using an NVIDIA tool named cuobjdump to extract the GPU assembly code and its hex representation. The hex representation is used to create a new file that contains only the opcode of the GPU assembly commands.

The performance evaluation of the PCIe monitoring system is compared with an implementation of the Aho-Corasick algorithm executing on a CPU and, more specifically, with the SNORT Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) tool, which is being fully optimized, publicly available, and in its core functionality to find patterns based on a set of rules is using the Aho-Corasick algorithm, since it is considered state-of-the-art.

A. Functional Verification

The process of verifying the functional demands of the PCIe monitoring system involves cross-validating numerous samples as input, containing typical cases and edge cases with the results taken from the FPGA board using a System Integrated Logic Analyzer (System ILA) to check the most important signals of the IP core of the Aho-Corasick pattern matching engine.

B. Evaluation Setup

The platforms where the algorithm of Aho-Corasick is being evaluated are an Intel CPU i5 of the 13th generation with frequency of 4300 MHz, and an FPGA board of the Kintex 7-series family named kc705 with frequency of 100 MHz.

C. Power and Energy Consumption

Power and energy consumption are calculated using the Linux tool, named perf, on the Intel CPU, which needs root privileges to run. It leverages the feature of Intel CPUs to measure the energy consumption of an executable program in Joules by writing the measurements in a specific directory in Linux. The perf tool calculates the power and energy consumption of the Aho-Corasick algorithm, given diverse inputs of different sizes and the result of the tool.

TABLE II
POWER CONSUMPTION OF PCIe MONITORING SYSTEM (WATTS)

PCIe monitoring system	Overall	GTX	Hard IP	Dynamic
1 AC IP core	2.267	1.253	0.058	0.773
2 AC IP cores	2.294	1.253	0.058	0.800

The power and energy consumption calculation in the FPGA board uses the power produced from Xilinx Vivado Suite by leveraging the type of power $p = E/t$ measured in Watts, where E is the symbol of energy and t is the time needed. It is observed that the power consumption increases according to the rise in the number of IP cores of the AC from 2.267 W to 2.294 W. In addition, the power consumption increase is in the dynamic region and neither in the Hard IP nor the GTX region. This happens because the overall design is the same in the two cases, with the only difference being the number of AC IP cores. Another significant observation is that the greater percentage of power consumption in the FPGA board happens in the GTX region because the GTX transceivers are used for the PCIe IP core. Table II presents the numerical values of the PCIe monitoring system's power consumption for 1 and 2 AC IP cores.

Figure 8 illustrates the energy consumption of the Aho-Corasick (AC) algorithm in the compared platforms. In the FPGA board KC705, there are two distinct cases: one with 1 IP core of Aho-Corasick and another one with 2 IP cores of Aho-Corasick. The energy consumption of the Aho-Corasick in the CPU is much more energy-consuming than that of implementing the same algorithm in the FPGA board. This is happening because, in the system, the CPU functions need much more power than a single FPGA. Specifically, it requires approximately 30 Watts (W) to run the algorithm of Aho-Corasick, while the FPGA needs from 2.267 W to 2.294 W, corresponding to 1 IP core of AC and 2 IP cores of AC. The increase in the power consumption in the FPGA board is rational because it needs 2x times more resources to implement two cores of AC than the implementation of 1 core of AC.

Consequently, the CPU needs $x275$ times more energy than an FPGA, which uses a single IP core of Aho-Corasick for the same input. On the other hand, when the FPGA uses 2 IP cores of Aho-Corasick, it needs $543x$ times less energy than the CPU. This obnoxious behavior may feel a little bit strange. However, it is utterly rational since using two IP cores of Aho-Corasick running in parallel can reduce the

Fig. 8. Energy Consumption Diagram

Fig. 10. Latency of Aho-Corasick in the Compared Platforms

Fig. 9. Resources Utilization of PCIe monitoring system

Fig. 11. Processing Throughput of Aho-Corasick in the Compared Platforms

algorithm’s computation time in half without considering the I/O consumption.

D. Resources Utilization

The resources of the PCIe monitoring system have been calculated through the Xilinx Vivado Suite for the two cases: one with 1 AC IP core and the other with 2 AC IP cores.

Comparing the total resources needed for both implementations of the PCIe monitoring system using 1 AC IP core and 2 AC IP cores, it can be shown that using two cores of AC requires more resources than using one core, which is utterly expected. Figure 9 illustrates this rise of resources of the FPGA board in the case of the 2 AC IP cores in contrast with the case of the 1 AC IP core. However, it seems that compared to the whole PCIe design, this rise is a very small fraction compared to the total design.

E. Throughput and Latency

The latency and processing throughput of the Aho-Corasick algorithm are calculated using the two compared platforms, i.e., the CPU and the FPGA board. To leverage the potential of the FPGA board to parallelize tasks, two AC IP cores have been used, tested, and evaluated in the computational performance of the algorithm.

Figures 10, 11 illustrate the computational performance of the Aho-Corasick operating on the compared platforms using the metrics of latency and processing throughput. The performance of the Aho-Corasick algorithm in the FPGA board

using two AC IP cores is faster and has greater processing throughput than the implementation in the CPU and in the FPGA of 1 AC IP core. Furthermore, it can be observed from the latency and processing throughput graphs that both of these metrics are better in the CPU than in the FPGA when using 1 AC IP core.

Another significant observation is that the processing throughput of the AC executing on the FPGA board using two AC IP cores is greater than the throughput of the CPU, which is expected since the latency was higher. According to the execution times required, the processing throughput of the FPGA board using one AC IP core is worse than that of the FPGA board with two AC IP cores and the CPU.

The acceleration of the FPGA execution using two AC IP cores compared to the CPU implementation of the Aho-Corasick Algorithm is $\times 1.55$, and the speedup of the responding processing throughput is $\times 1.55$ compared to the CPU.

Overall, the final performance of the Aho-Corasick algorithm used to monitor PCIe traffic is better than the corresponding implementation of the algorithm when executed on the CPU. The final speed-up of execution time in the specific FPGA board is $\times 1.55$ compared to the CPU, and the speed-up of the processing throughput is approximately $\times 1.55$ compared to the CPU. Furthermore, the implementation in the FPGA board using two AC IP cores is energy efficient compared to the CPU by a factor of $\times 543$ times less energy consumed than the CPU. Finally, the Aho-Corasick IP core uses a

minimum amount of resources, making it an excellent choice for monitoring, and it can be leveraged by using multiple AC IP cores to parallel the process and make it faster.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

With many companies and services investing in building data centers consisting of hundreds of thousands of diverse accelerators, including FPGAs, and GPUs, many developers and researchers rely on using these accelerators instead of buying costly products to execute heavy load computational tasks for the same work. The problem that emerges is that when using these accelerators, the providers need to ensure the secure code execution of the customer's applications, the confidentiality and integrity of the user's data, and the availability of the accelerators. With this work, we propose a PCIe protocol-based monitoring mechanism that detects GPU miners by identifying sequences of GPU instructions that indicate such activity. The proposed PCIe monitoring tool achieves better performance than the corresponding state-of-the-art implementation in a CPU by an overall latency speedup of $\times 1.55$, and it is more energy efficient by 543 times than the CPU's implementation while occupying limited hardware resources.

As future work, we will replace the current GPU emulation with a softcore GPU, as it serves only as a memory for storing GPU binary code. This approach will be energy efficient, maintaining comparable execution time to traditional GPUs. In addition, more streaming channels will provide the capability to partially reconfigure the state table of Aho-Corasick IP cores use and, therefore, the set of rules, giving the administrator of the monitoring system the ability to modify the rules during runtime. Moreover, since the monitoring system requires minimal resources to function effectively, it will be integrated into a real heterogeneous system consisting of a CPU and a GPU. This will be achieved by incorporating a PCIe interposer with a Programmable Logic (PL) component between them and embedding the monitoring system within the interposer, enabling it to monitor PCIe traffic between the CPU and GPU. As a result this work could be also used in an embedded system consisting of different parts which in one of them have an FPGA logic. Finally, this work can lead to further analysis of malicious GPU applications beyond miners, exploring how they can be detected at the instruction level using this runtime monitoring system.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the projects MEDIANE and EMERALDS, funded by the European Commission under GA No. 101168465 and 101093051, respectively. It also received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking under the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under GA No. 101139067. This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which maybe made of the information contained therein.

This is a preprint version of the paper accepted to appear in the 2025 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (CSR) proceedings with DOI 10.1109/CSR64739.2025.11130157

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